

DEVELOPMENT OF A DECENTRALISED ELECTRONIC VOTING RESULT TRANSMISSION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Electronic voting (e-voting) systems have presented significant breakthroughs to the limitations of traditional paper-based voting methods, particularly in improving the process of vote collation and transmission. However, centralized e-voting processes are still susceptible to several challenges, such as the susceptibility to a Single Point of Failure (SPOF) and potential manipulation of results, which can undermine trust in the electoral process. This work addressed these issues by designing and implementing a bi-modal electronic voting result transmission system that leverages both Telegram and Firebase for real-time, simultaneous vote transmission. The system integrated Arduino Mega and NodeMCU microcontrollers with a Thin Film Transistor (TFT) display to enable voters to cast their votes securely. The results generated were transmitted to both Telegram and Firebase, ensuring redundancy and reducing the risk of SPOF, thereby providing a higher degree of security and improved integrity of transmitted data. Testing results demonstrated that the system accurately transmitted votes in real time to both platforms. This study addressed the critical need for a secure, reliable and trustworthy voting process.

Keywords: Electronic Voting, Single Point of Failure (SPOF), Decentralization, Election Results Transmission.

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1.0: Introduction

There has always been a need to make choices, and voting is one of the ways by which choices are made. E-voting came into existence due to the limitations of the security of results during the collation and transmission of a manual voting method (Arthur *et al.*, 2020). Voting is a fundamental aspect of any democratic society, allowing citizens to express their preferences and participate in the decision-making process (Pankevych *et al.*, 2021). Voting decisions are fundamental to democratic societies because they influence the form and composition of governments and establish the laws governing humankind (Kulachai *et al.*, 2023).

Over 50% of the world's nations are categorised as democratic nations, granting eligible citizens the right to exercise their voting power and ensuring that the election process is trustworthy, impenetrable, and free of bias (Arthur *et al.*, 2020; Zaghloul *et al.*, 2021). Elections have been conducted in the past decade using the paper-based voting technique (ballot box election or traditional voting technique) and polling centres to determine the winner of the election (Adewale *et al.*, 2020; Arthur *et al.*, 2020).

In Nigeria, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) presented different technologies like the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) along with the INEC Voter Enrolment Device (IVED) and INEC Results Viewing Portal (IReV) to improve the 2023 presidential election in curbing election malpractices (majorly manipulation of result during transmission and collation) (Dii, 2023). The BVAS was used to accredit voters and transmit results electronically. IVED was used for enrolling eligible voters, and the IReV platform offered real-time access to election results online. According to Acheampong (2023), the technologies performed satisfactorily during the mock tests but on election day, technical challenges came up that affected the election process.

Despite the implementation of these technologies, human interference was not eliminated, which is at variance with the basic ideology behind electronic voting (Dii, 2023). Paper ballots were used for election result counting, while the results of the counted ballot were written on the result (Acheampong, 2023). This method and technology did not proffer the needed solution to e-voting systems as there was the possibility of result manipulation during the collation and transmission. Figure 1 shows BVAS which was used for voter authentication. A major breakthrough to the challenge of centralized database system is the application of blockchain technology. According to Shobowale *et al.*, (2024), Blockchain technology holds basic features such as decentralized network, absence of third party, improved security and distributed database.

Some advantages of e-voting over the traditional voting system include fast and accurate vote counting, an increase in election reliability and a reduction in the amount of paper, thereby reducing cost and making it environmentally friendly (Jafar *et al.*, 2021; Risnanto *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1: A voter using BVAS for authentication

Direct-recording electronic (DRE) voting machines allow voters to cast their votes directly onto a computerised interface, like a touchscreen or other input device, to make their selections (Wolf *et al.*, 2011). It can be equipped with a Voter Verifiable Paper Audit Trail (VVPAT), which is a paper record of each vote cast that provides a physical record of the votes that can be used for audits or recounts, as used in the United States of America and Netherlands (Adewale *et al.*, 2020; Risnanto *et al.*, 2022). The DRE can also be referred to as an Electronic Voting Machine (EVM) (Wolf *et al.*, 2011).

Other types of e-voting systems exist, such as Mix-net-Based e-voting which helps to ensure the anonymity of voters by using an anonymous channel for anonymous communication, thereby preventing eavesdropping. The e-voting system shuffles all the votes together and sends the ballots back in a random order without knowing which vote came from whom (Kho *et al.*, 2022), Homomorphic e-voting makes use of the homomorphism property such that certain mathematical operations can be performed directly on the cipher/encrypted text (Kharel, 2020; Kho *et al.*, 2022; Park & Satt, 2022), Blind Signature-Based e-voting which is a type of digital signature that allows a vote to be “blinded” or encrypted in a way that hides the content of the vote from the voting authority who signs it without knowing the actual vote choice of the voter (Kho *et al.*, 2022). According to Jafar *et al.*, (2021), blockchain-based e-voting offers a decentralised node for online voting, which is beneficiary for end-to-end verification.

Trust, efficiency and safety are the three main attractions of the electronic transmission of election results in Nigeria (Maria & Tolulope, 2021). Improving transparency, accountability, and auditing through electronic result transmission logically suggests a reduction in disputed outcomes (INEC, 2021).

Integrity, eligibility, robustness, universal verifiability availability, anonymity, fairness, receipt-freeness, security, voter verifiability, and correctness/accuracy are basic technical requirements of e-voting systems (Ahmad *et al.*, 2020; Olaniyi *et al.*, 2022; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2023). However, existing centralised systems or Single Point access systems for e-voting make the system vulnerable to SPOF, denial of service (DoS), and distributed DoS (DDoS) attacks

(Elisa *et al.*, 2023; Olaniyi *et al.*, 2022). Lahane *et al.* (2020) presented a comprehensive study on blockchain technology applications in e-voting systems. The authors proposed an e-voting model that leverages blockchain technology in addressing issues of vote rigging, hacking of electronic voting machines (EVMs), election manipulation, and booth capturing.

Sheela & Franklin (2021) proposed homomorphic encryption and fingerprint e-voting system authentication to enhance security and authenticity in elections. The proposed system was said to address issues with traditional voting methods and electronic voting machines, suggesting biometrics as a solution for secure and transparent elections. Dagwar *et al.* (2022) proposed a system that aims to improve the security and accuracy of voting using a Node MCU mega controller, GPS module, fingerprint module, and power supply. The work claimed to address most of the issues faced in election systems but focused more on the voter authentication side, stating different biometrics that can be used.

Braimoh *et al.* (2022) presented a system that incorporates biometrics to enhance the electoral process in Nigeria, discussing the challenges faced by the existing voting systems, thereby proposing the use of e-ballots and biometrics to address these issues. The paper presented a novel approach to voting systems, aiming to improve the integrity and security of the elections in Nigeria. Satizábal *et al.* (2022) proposed a Secure Internet Voting Protocol (SIVP) that would be designed for electoral processes in Colombia. The protocol employed the use of public key cryptography and blind signatures to ensure secure and transparent elections. The paper gave a deep insight into securing votes over the Internet during transmission but did not provide a means of decentralising the votes.

Jafar *et al.* (2021) discussed the application of blockchain technology in addressing electronic voting issues, offering decentralised and end-to-end node verification advantages. The work highlighted the shift towards electronic voting methods to increase voter participation and trust while ensuring the democratic process remained transparent and fair.

The arrangement of the rest of the paper is such that 2.0 describes the research methodology employed in the paper for both the hardware and software implementations. Item 3.0 discusses the results generated and their implications, while item 4.0 presents the conclusion and recommendation for future work.

2.0 Methodology

The Arduino Mega 2560 was interfaced with an ILI9341 TFT (Thin Film Transistors) touchscreen display and NodeMCU Wi-Fi Module. The Bimodal system used was Firebase Database and Telegram, using APIs that would enable the votes to be sent to both systems in real time. Arduino Mega microcontroller was used for programming and control of the connected hardware components while the NodeMCU acted as the Wi-Fi Module used to send the voting result to the selected Bimodal systems. The TFT Liquid Crystal Display (TFT-LCD) Touch screen was used for display and voting. Figure 2 indicates the flow of the process carried out.

Figure 2: System Flow Diagram.

2.1: System design

The system was designed using Fritzing platform to design the system based on the components used and necessary calculations done for the components to work appropriately, which marks the initial step for the implementation of the system. Figure 3 represents the Fritzing design carried out with the necessary connections made.

Figure 3: System design on Fritzing

2.1.1: Hardware implementation of the system

Based on the design, the components were put together using a breadboard and jumper wires for easy connection of the required components. The components used were an Arduino Mega 2560, 2.8” ILI9341 TFT Display, NodeMCU development board and 7 5.1K Ω and 3.21K Ω resistors.

The TFT screen had pin configurations for connection to an Arduino Mega 2560. The various components were connected with the aid of the breadboard and the jumper wires based on the pin configuration for connection of the components, which resulted in the physical implementation.

2.1.2: Software implementation of the system

Arduino IDE, using C++ programming language, was used to code the Arduino Mega 2560 and NodeMCU development board to interface with the TFT display to accept input from the display in the form of a selection of the required party an individual is voting for to activate counting, collating and transmission of the votes to 2 social media platforms for easy viewing of the result and also to avoid SPOF.

Code was written for the TFT display to display sample parties- “Mango”, “Banana”, and “Apple”- which was then compiled and uploaded to the Arduino Mega 2560. Figure 4 shows the TFT screen displaying the sample parties. The code was then modified to different sections, such as the landing page for the system, the voting page and the page congratulating a voter on their selection before it goes back to the landing page.

Figure 4: Design on the TFT Display showing the sample parties.

Code was uploaded to the NodeMCU to count, collate and send the votes to the two databases. Code uploaded to the Arduino Mega 2560 included lines of code intended to send the selected party, which was given an identification number, such that APC has an identification number of 1, to the serial monitor where the NodeMCU will read the identification number and identifies the identification number assigned to each party. Botfather was used on Telegram to create a new bot that was used to receive the voting results in real time. Firebase Database was used to store and update the vote in real-time.

The NodeMCU does the collation of the result based on the number of unique IDs for each party and sends it to the chatbot on Telegram and Firebase Database, including collation for each party altogether instead of manually counting the number of times each party appears, which is still susceptible to manipulation either intentionally or unintentionally. The last result sent on both platforms after voting had been concluded was verified for the two systems to ensure accuracy. If they do not tally, it is evident that the votes were manipulated, and the result would not be accepted.

3.0: Results and Discussion

The system was tested in a use-case scenario. The voter, on reaching the system is met with a welcome page and then a “Click Me” button as shown in Figure 5. When the button is selected

Figure 5: TFT Display showing the welcome page

using the stylus pen, the page for the selection of the party intended by the voter is shown. Three parties were captured for the sake of this work namely: PDP, APC and NNPC. The nomenclature of sample parties selected and the results generated are purely based on research work for the purpose of this project without affiliation to or interest of any existing party in mind. Figure 6 shows the parties being displayed on the TFT display. The voter is then prompted to select their intended party. After the selection is made, a confirmation page is displayed acknowledging the voter selection, and then the system returns to the welcome page.

Figure 6: TFT Display showing the sample parties

3.1: System Result Testing

After the selection of the intended party by the user on the TFT, the serial monitor of the Arduino reads the selection made and shows the selected party's Identity instead of the party name itself. The inputted identity is a private key only known to authorised users to hide the display of the exact party each voter votes for. This is to create a level of confidentiality and privacy, thereby eradicating the possibility of voters' preferences being easily identified by onlookers or voting agents. For this work, the following identities were allocated to parties as indicated below:

- 1 is for APC
- 2 is for PDP
- 3 is for NNPC

The NodeMCU reads the ID, does the vote collation for each party and sends it to Telegram and Firebase at the same time via Wi-Fi.

Figure 7 shows the results generated from the NodeMCU readings on the Arduino Mega serial monitor, indicating the total votes for the selected party and displaying the incremented value

of the votes as each voter selects his/her preferred party. The updating of votes is done in step 1 such that for every party identity indicated, the vote for such party is increased by one (1), and the updated vote is displayed and transmitted to authorised databases.

The Telegram message had a compilation of the votes for each party, sending a new update on the result when any voter has made a selection during voting. Firebase was updating the results of each party in real time as voters kept making selections. After the voting process, the votes sent to Telegram and Firebase were checked to ascertain their accuracy. Figure 8 presents results sent to Telegram, and Figure 9 shows the Firebase results.

Figure 7: NodeMCU reading the output from the serial monitor of the Arduino Mega

Figure 8: Result sent to Telegram in real-time

Figure 9: Result sent to Firebase in real-time

The results presented from the implemented system validated its decentralised nature, ensuring improved security, enhanced efficiency and better usability, presenting accurate results to two platforms in real time which has proven to be of better performance compared to existing systems. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there has not been any published work on decentralised transmission of electronic votes via Firebase and Telegram, as presented in this paper, which makes it a novel work.

4.0: Conclusion and Recommendation

The design of the bimodal e-voting result transmission system, which led to the implementation of the system by the integration of the software and hardware components using two databases to avoid SPOF and reduce vote manipulation during collation and transmission, was successfully carried out. The work which focuses on result transmission via decentralised modes is premised on the assumption that each voter had been authenticated. Testing of the system was done, which achieved the goal of transmitting result votes in a real time scenario to authorised two databases simultaneously. The system is capable of capturing and displaying all available votes via both the Telegram and Firebase platforms. The findings of this study contributed to the development of more robust e-voting systems, ultimately strengthening democratic processes and ensuring that election results accurately reflect the will of the people. The work concluded with recommendations for further enhancements, including the incorporation of additional transmission systems, advanced security mechanisms, and a web interface for broader accessibility.

This study significantly advances the field of electronic voting by addressing vulnerabilities in centralised databases, specifically the risks of SPOF and result manipulation. It introduces a bimodal voting result transmission system using two separate databases, enhancing reliability and integrity. The innovative integration of Telegram and Firebase for secure, real-time transmission of voting results provides a practical framework for future research. By proposing robust security solutions to key vulnerabilities, the study enhances the transparency and trustworthiness of the electoral process, fostering greater public confidence. Practical implementation and testing of the system offer valuable real-world insights, ensuring that the theoretical contributions are available for practical use. The methodologies and findings lay a foundational framework for future research, guiding efforts to improve the security, efficiency, and reliability of e-voting systems.

The full-scale implementation of the system can be improved upon by including more systems the votes would be sent to, as well as including security mechanisms like encryption. The system can be enhanced to include an authentication mechanism for a full-scale voting experience. The inclusion of a website for easy access to the result from any location can be considered for a wider scale view.

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